

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

№4 (2)

ISSN: 2992-8982

<https://yashil-iqtisodiyot-taraqqiyot.uz/>

2026

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Bosh muharrir:

Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich

Elektron nashr. 2026-yil, aprel.

Bosh muharrir o'rinbosari:

Karimov Norboy G'aniyevich

Muharrir:

Qurbonov Sherzod Ismatillayevich

Tahrir hay'ati:

Salimov Oqil Umrzoqov, O'zbekiston Fanlar akademiyasi akademigi
Abduraxmanov Kalandar Xodjayevich, O'zbekiston Fanlar akademiyasi akademigi
Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich, texnika fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Rae Kvon Chung, Janubiy Koreya, TDIU faxriy professori, "Nobel" mukofoti laureati
Osman Mesten, Turkiya parlamenti a'zosi, Turkiya – O'zbekiston do'stlik jamiyati rahbari
Axmedov Durbek Kudratillayevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Axmedov Sayfullo Normatovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Abduraxmanova Gulnora Kalandarovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Kalonov Muxiddin Baxritdinovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Siddiqova Sadoqat G'afforovna, pedagogika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
Xudoyqulov Sadirdin Karimovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Maxmudov Nosir, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Yuldashev Mutallib Ibragimovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Samadov Asqarjon Nishonovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, professor
Slizovskiy Dimitriy Yegorovich, texnika fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Mustafakulov Sherzod Igamberdiyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Axmedov Ikrom Akramovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Eshtayev Alisher Abdug'aniyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Xajiyev Baxtiyor Dushaboyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Hakimov Nazar Hakimovich, falsafa fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Musayeva Shoirazimovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), professor
Ali Konak (Ali Ko'nak), iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor (Turkiya)
Cham Tat Huei, falsafa fanlari doktori (PhD), professor (Malayziya)
Foziljonov Ibrohimjon Sotvoldix'ja o'g'li, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dots.
Faxridinov Zafarjon Faxridin o'g'li, O'zb. Res. Bosh prokuraturasi HIJQKD boshqarma boshlig'i
Utayev Uktam Choriyevich, Anijon viloyati prokurorining o'rinbosari
Ochilov Farkhod, O'zb. Res. Bosh prokuraturasi IJQK Departamentining Namangan viloyati boshqarmasi boshlig'i
Buzrukxonov Sarvarxon Munavvarxonovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent
Axmedov Javohir Jamolovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
Toxirov Jaloliddin Ochil o'g'li, texnika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), katta o'qituvchi
Bobobekov Ergash Abdumalikovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), v.b. dots.
Djudi Smetana, pedagogika fanlari nomzodi, dotsent (AQSH)
Krissi Lyuis, pedagogika fanlari nomzodi, dotsent (AQSH)
Glazova Marina Viktorovna, Iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (Moskva)
Nosirova Nargiza Jamoliddin qizi, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Sevil Piriyeva Karaman, falsafa fanlari doktori (PhD) (Turkiya)
Mirzaliyev Sanjar Makhamatjon o'g'li, TDIU ITI departamenti rahbari
Ochilov Bobur Baxtiyor o'g'li, TDIU katta o'qituvchisi
Golisheva Yelena Vyacheslavovna, Iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent.
Abdulkarimova Dinara Rustamxonovna, bank-moliya akademiyasi professori, DSc., professor.
Ikramov Murod Akramovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Nazarova Ra'no Rustamovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Editorial board:

Salimov Okil Umrzokovich, Academician of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan
Abdurakhmanov Kalandar Khodjayevich, Academician of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan
Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich, Doctor of Technical Sciences (DSc), Professor
Rae Kwon Chung, South Korea, Honorary Professor at TSUE, Nobel Prize Laureate
Osman Mesten, Member of the Turkish Parliament, Head of the Turkey–Uzbekistan Friendship Society
Akhmedov Durbek Kudratillayevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Akhmedov Sayfullo Normatovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Abdurakhmanova Gulnora Kalandarovna, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Kalonov Mukhiddin Bakhridinovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Siddikova Sadokat Gafforovna, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Pedagogical Sciences
Khudoykulov Sadirdin Karimovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Makhmudov Nosir, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Yuldashev Mutallib Ibragimovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Samadov Askarjon Nishonovich, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Professor
Slizovskiy Dmitriy Yegorovich, Doctor of Technical Sciences (DSc), Professor
Mustafakulov Sherzod Igamberdiyevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Akhmedov Ikrom Akramovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Eshtayev Alisher Abduganiyevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Khajiyev Bakhtiyor Dushaboyevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Khakimov Nazar Khakimovich, Doctor of Philosophy (DSc), Professor
Musayeva Shoira Azimovna, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Professor
Ali Konak, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor (Turkey)
Cham Tat Huei, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD), Professor (Malaysia)
Foziljonov Ibrokhimjon Sotvoldikhoja ugli, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Fakhriddinov Zafarjon Fakhriddin ogli, Head of the DCEC under the Prosecutor General's Office of the Rep. of Uzb.
Utayev Uktam Choriyevich, Deputy Prosecutor of Anijan Region
Ochilov Farkhod, Head of the Namangan Regional Department of the Department of Internal Affairs of Rep. of Uzb.
Buzrukkhonov Sarvarkhon Munavvarkhonovich, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Akhmedov Javokhir Jamolovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences
Tokhirov Jaloliddin Ochil ugli, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Technical Sciences, Senior Lecturer
Bobobekov Ergash Abdumalikovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Acting Associate Professor
Judi Smetana, Candidate of Pedagogical Sciences, Associate Professor (USA)
Chrissy Lewis, Candidate of Pedagogical Sciences, Associate Professor (USA)
Glazova Marina Victorovna, Doctor of Sciences in Economics (Moscow)
Nosirova Nargiza Jamoliddin kizi, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Sevil Piriyeva Karaman, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) (Turkey)
Mirzaliyev Sanjar Makhamatjon ugli, Head of the Department of Scientific Research and Innovations, TSUE
Ochilov Bobur Bakhtiyor ugli, Senior lecturer at TSUI
Golisheva Yelena Vyacheslavovna, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor.
Abdukarimova Dinara Rustamkhanovna, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Ikramov Murod Akramovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Nazarova Ra'no Rustamovna, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor

Ekspertlar kengashi:

Berkinov Bazarbay, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Po'latov Baxtiyor Alimovich, texnika fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Aliyev Bekdavlat Aliyevich, falsafa fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Isakov Janabay Yakubbayevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Xalikov Suyun Ravshanovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent
Rustamov Ilhomiddin, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent
Hakimov Ziyodulla Ahmadovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, dotsent
Kamilova Iroda Xusniddinovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
G'afurov Doniyor Orifovich, pedagogika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
Fayziyev Oybek Raximovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Tuxtabayev Jamshid Sharafetdinovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Xamidova Faridaxon Abdulkarim qizi, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, dotsent
Yaxshiboyeva Laylo Abdisattorovna, katta o'qituvchi
Babayeva Zuhra Yuldashevna, mustaqil tadqiqotchi
Komilova Nilufar Karshiboyevna, Geografiya fanlari doktori, professori
Umirzoqov Ja'sur Artiqboy o'g'li, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), dotsent
Zebo Kuldasheva, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), dotsent

Board of Experts:

Berkinov Bazarbay, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Pulatov Bakhtiyor Alimovich, Doctor of Technical Sciences (DSc), Professor
Aliyev Bekdavlat Aliyevich, Doctor of Philosophy (DSc), Professor
Isakov Janabay Yakubbayevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Khalikov Suyun Ravshanovich, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Rustamov Ilhomiddin, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Khakimov Ziyodulla Akhmadovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Kamilova Iroda Xusniddinovna, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economics
Gafurov Doniyor Orifovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Pedagogy
Fayziyev Oybek Raximovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economics, Associate Professor
Tukhtabayev Jamshid Sharafetdinovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economics, Associate Professor
Khamidova Faridaxon Abdulkarimovna, Doctor of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Yakhshiboyeva Laylo Abdisattorovna, Senior Lecturer
Babayeva Zuhra Yuldashevna, Independent Researcher
Komilova Nilufar Karshiboyevna, Doctor of Geographical Sciences, Professor
Umirzokov Jasur Artiqboy ugli, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Associate Professor
Zebo Kuldasheva, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Associate Professor

- 08.00.01 Iqtisodiyot nazariyasi
- 08.00.02 Makroiqtisodiyot
- 08.00.03 Sanoat iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.04 Qishloq xo'jaligi iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.05 Xizmat ko'rsatish tarmoqlari iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.06 Ekonometrika va statistika
- 08.00.07 Moliya, pul muomalasi va kredit
- 08.00.08 Buxgalteriya hisobi, iqtisodiy tahlil va audit
- 08.00.09 Jahon iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.10 Demografiya. Mehnat iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.11 Marketing
- 08.00.12 Mintaqaviy iqtisodiyot
- 08.00.13 Menejment
- 08.00.14 Iqtisodiyotda axborot tizimlari va texnologiyalari
- 08.00.15 Tadbirkorlik va kichik biznes iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.16 Raqamli iqtisodiyot va xalqaro raqamli integratsiya
- 08.00.17 Turizm va mehmonxona faoliyati

Muassis: "Ma'rifat-print-media" MChJ

Hamkorlarimiz: Toshkent davlat iqtisodiyot universiteti, O'zR Tabiat resurslari vazirligi, O'zR Bosh prokuraturasi huzuridagi IJQK departamenti.

Jurnalning ilmiyligi:

“Yashil” iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot” jurnali

O'zbekiston Respublikasi Oliy ta'lim, fan va innovatsiyalar vazirligi huzuridagi Oliy attestatsiya komissiyasi rayosatining 2023-yil 1-apreldagi 336/3-sonli qarori bilan ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

MUNDARIJA

RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOTDA “AKT XIZMATLARI” TUSHUNCHASI VA ULARNING EKSPORT SALOHİYATI.....	14
Shermatov Sherzod Xotamovich RAQAMLI MARKETING STRATEGIYALARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH ORQALI KORXONALAR RAQOBATBARDOSHLIGINI OSHIRISH MEXANIZMLARI	20
Amonov Mirzohid Tuymuratovich, Xodjayev Anvar Rasulovich TIJORAT BANKLARINING BYUDJET MABLAG‘LARI HISOBIGA MOLİYALASHTIRILADIGAN LOYIHALARDAGI ISHTIROKINI KUCHAYTIRISH MEXANIZMLARI	26
Maxmudov Rahimjon Hamid o‘g‘li KORPORATIV BOSHQARUV SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISHNING STRATEGIK YO‘NALISHLARI.....	33
Shakirova Gulbaxor Sharipdjanovna YASHIL IQTISODIYOTGA O‘TISHDA XORIJIY TAJRIBALAR TAHLILI VA UNI O‘ZBEKISTON SHAROITIDA QO‘LLASH IMKONIYATLARI	38
Ne‘matova Mavsuma, Xolmamatov Diyorbek ВЛИЯНИЕ НАЛОГООБЛОЖЕНИЯ НА ИНВЕСТИЦИОННУЮ АКТИВНОСТЬ ПРОМЫШЛЕННЫХ ПРЕДПРИЯТИЙ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ.....	43
Буранова Лола Вахобовна ФИНТЕХ-ЭКОСИСТЕМА КАК ФАКТОР ИНКЛЮЗИВНОГО И УСТОЙЧИВОГО РАЗВИТИЯ ЭКОНОМИКИ УЗБЕКИСТАНА: СТРУКТУРНЫЙ АНАЛИЗ И ПЕРСПЕКТИВЫ ТРАНСФОРМАЦИИ	54
Эшмуротов Дониёр Ихтиёр угли ZAMONAVIY MARKETING KONSEPSIYALARI ASOSIDA XIZMATLAR RAQOBATBARDOSHLIGINING USLUBIY JIHATLARI.....	60
Ostonaqulova Gulsaraxon Matyoqub qizi, Fayzullayeva Zamira Alijonovna XIZMAT KO‘RSATISH KORXONALARINING IQTISODIY XAVFSIZLIGINI TA‘MINLASHDA SERVIS XAVFSIZLIGI INDEKSI: SAMARQAND VILOYATI MISOLIDA	64
Shodmanova Zubayda Ubaydullayevna QURILISH FAOLIYATI SOHALARIDA RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALARDAN FOYDALANISHNING ILG‘OR XORIJIY TAJRIBALARI	
Xusanov Kamoliddin Xolmamat o‘g‘li INSON KAPITALI VA KADRLAR SALOHİYATINI BOSHQARISHNING NAZARIY KONSEPSIYALARI	73
Abdullo Sohobov O‘ZBEKISTONDA URBANIZATSIYA JARAYONLARI JADALLASHUVI VA UNING HUDUDIY XUSUSIYATLARI	84
Mamanazarov Oybek Shomurodovich KORXONALAR MOLİYAVIY HOLATINI MOLİYAVIY HISOBOTNING XALQARO STANDARTLARI (MHXS) ASOSIDA BAHOLASHNING NAZARIY-METODOLOGIK ASOSLARI	91
Xamidov Javoxir Shavkat o‘g‘li BIZNES JARAYONLARINI MONITORING QILISH TIZIMINING HOZIRGI HOLATI TAHLILI.....	95
Dadajonova Madina Ravshan qizi O‘ZBEKISTON VA XORIJIY MAMLAKATLARDA BENEFITSIAR MULKDOR KONSEPSIYASINI QO‘LLASHNING DOLZARB MASALALARI	100
Ochilov Farhod Malikovich O‘ZBEKISTONDA YASHIL IQTISODIYOTGA O‘TISHNING MAKROIQTISODIY SAMARADORLIGINI BAHOLASH (GDP, BANDLIK VA INVESTITSIYALAR KESIMIDA).....	106
Hayitov Jamshid Xolboyevich	

INVESTITSION JOZIBADORLIKKA TA'SIR QILUVCHI OMILLAR TAHLILI.....	111
Mamatqulova Hafiza Bahodir qizi IPOTEKA BOZORI MUAMMOLARINING EMPERIK TAHLILI VA ULARNI BARTARAF ETISH STRATEGIYALARI.....	118
Olokulova Feruza Mansurovna, Safarova Dilrabo Baxriddin qizi MILLIY IQTISODIYOT RAQOBATIDA NAZARIY VA AMALIY QARASHLAR.....	122
Karimova Iroda Abdusattarovna KORPORATIV BANK XIZMATLARIGA INNOVATSION TEXNOLOGIYALAR HAMDA ZAMONAVIY BIZNES MODELLARNI JORIY ETISHNING STRATEGIK YO'NALISHLARI.....	128
Qurbonov Abror Abdullayevich GREEN ECONOMY DEVELOPMENT IN UZBEKISTAN AND INDONESIA: A COMPARATIVE STUDY.....	133
Ibrokhimova Iroda Ikromjon Kizi. Askolani. Javliyev Nuriddin Bektemir o'g'li AHOLI BANDLIGINI TA'MINLASHDA REKRUTING AGENTLIKLARINING O'RNI.....	142
Sherkulova Nodirabegim Baxordin qizi ФАКТОРЫ ТЕКУЧЕСТИ КАДРОВ И МЕХАНИЗМЫ УДЕРЖАНИЯ ПЕРСОНАЛА В СОВРЕМЕННЫХ ОРГАНИЗАЦИЯХ УЗБЕКИСТАНА.....	148
Джураева Гузаль Шавкатовна BUDJET DAROMADLARI TARKIBIDAGI SOLIQLARNING ULUSHINI BOSHQARISH.....	156
Abduraxmonova Gulmira Sobir qizi RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOT SHAROITIDA AVTOSERVIS SHOHOVCHALARINI BOSHQARISHNI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	161
Marqayev Xurshid Aliqulovich THE ECONOMIC NATURE OF HUMAN CAPITAL AND ITS RECOGNITION IN ACCOUNTING AS AN OBJECT OF ECONOMIC ANALYSIS.....	165
Zafar Qodirov Abdivaxobovich O'ZBEKISTON IQTISODIYOTIDA RAQAMLI TRANSFORMATSIYA JARAYONLARINING SAMARADORLIGINI BAHOLASH.....	170
Ibragimov G'ayrat Ablaqulovich. Tursunov Ozod Matlubovich Shukurova Nilufar Qahramonova IMPROVING THE EFFICIENCY OF INNOVATIVE SERVICES IN THE DIGITAL ECONOMY.....	175
Mirzaev Kulmamat Djanzakovich NODAVLAT NOTIJORAT TASHKILOTLARI MOLIYAVIY BARQARORLIGINI BAHOLASHDA INTEGRAL KO'RSATKICHLAR TIZIMINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	179
Aliyev Arslon Salom o'g'li A STUDY ON THE COLLABORATIVE MECHANISM OF DIGITAL ARCHIVES GOVERNANCE AND TALENT GOVERNANCE: AN ANALYSIS BASED ON JOB COMPETENCY, PERFORMANCE EVALUATION, AND ORGANIZATIONAL EFFECTIVENESS.....	184
Wang Biao USTAMA ISHLAB CHIQARISH XARAJATLARINING MAZMUNI VA UNI XALQARO STANDARTLARGA MUVOFIQ TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	190
Tashnazarova Dilfuza Samiddinovna INTEGRATSIIYA SAMARADORLIGINI O'LCHASHNING METODOLOGIK MODELI VA INDIKATORLAR TIZIMI.....	195
Aliqulov Abbas Baxtiyor o'g'li XIZMAT KO'RSATISH KORXONALARIDA RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALAR ASOSIDA XIZMATLAR SIFATINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	202
Xudoyorov Lochinbek Bahromovich	

MOLIYAVIY HISOBOTLAR AUDITINI XALQARO STANDARTLAR ASOSIDA TAKOMILLASHTIRISH ISTIQBOLLARI.....	207
Elomonov Dadaxon Ozodullayevich	
TO'QIMACHILIK SANOATI KORXONALARIDA IQTISODIY RESURLARDAN SAMARALI FOYDALANISH YO'LLARI	213
L.S. Azimova	
THEORETICAL AND METHODOLOGICAL FOUNDATIONS OF IFRS AND FINANCIAL REPORTING	218
Tojiboyev Abdullajon Kamoliddin o'g'li	
PAXTA-TO'QIMACHILIK SANOATIDA DAVLAT-XUSUSIY SHERIKLIKNING HUQUQIY ASOSLARI	223
Abdullayev Hamidulla Abdug'ani o'g'li	
TURIZM KORXONALARIDA XIZMATLAR SIFATINI OSHIRISH ORQALI RAQOBATBARDOSHLIKNI KUCHAYTIRISHNING ZAMONAVIY BOSHQARUV MEXANIZMLARI	227
Ergasheva Zarifa Baxtiyarovna	
CHO'L-YAYLOV CHORVACHILIGI MAJMUASI RIVOJLANTIRISH	232
Nurmanov Sherzod Xujayarovich	
KREDITORLAR REYTINGINI MASHINAVIY O'QITISHGA ASOSLANGAN BASHORATLASH ALGORITMLARI	237
Beknazarov Ulug'bek Zafar o'g'li	
MIKROIQTISODIYOTDA ISTE'MOLCHILAR XULQ-ATVORI VA TALAB SHAKLLANISHI OMILLARI	242
Raximov Azizbek Saliyevich	
OLIY TA'LIMNI MOLIYALASHTIRISHNING ILG'OR XORIJIY Tajribasi: AQSH MISOLIDA.....	246
Kurbanov Baxodir Negmatullayevich	
O'ZBEKISTON TURIZM INDUSTRIYASINI BOSHQARISHDA INNOVATSION YONDASHUVLARNI JORIY ETISH USULLARI	250
Ashurova Shaxnoza Almasovna	
RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOT SHAROITIDA OMMAVIY AXBOROT VOSITALARI KORXONALARINING MOLIYAVIY BARQARORLIGINI TA'MINLASHNING NAZARIY ASOSLARI.....	257
Sharipova Shahlo Istamovna	
XIZMAT KO'RSATISH KORXONALARIDA RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALAR ASOSIDA XIZMATLAR SIFATINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	262
Xudoyorov Lochinbek Bahromovich	
XIZMATLAR SOHASIDA MIJOZ QONIQLASHINI OSHIRISH MEXANIZMLARI: QORAQALPOG'ISTON RESPUBLIKASI MISOLIDA	278
Aqsungul Usenova Tenel qizi, Qoraqalpoq davlat universiteti	
Dawletmuratov Adilbay Mirzaboyevich	
O'ZBEKISTONDA QANDOLAT MAHSULOTLARI BOZORINING SHAKLLANISHI VA RIVOJLANISH XUSUSIYATLARI.....	283
Azlarova Munira Muhammad-Amin qizi	
TA'LIM XIZMATLARI BOZORINI SHAKLLANTIRISH, RIVOJLANTIRISH VA KO'RSATKICHLARINI O'RGANISH.....	289
Bozorova Madina Raxmat qizi	
IMPROVING SERVICE QUALITY MONITORING IN SERVICE ENTERPRISES BASED ON DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES	294
Xudoyorov Lochinbek Bahromovich	
KREDITLASH MEXANIZMINING ILMIY-NAZARIY ASOSLARI VA UNING TARIXIY RIVOJLANISH BOSQICHLARI	299
Ortiqov Husan Usmonaliyevich	

O'ZBEKISTONDA QIMMATLI QOG'OZLAR BOZORI MUAMMOLARI VA RIVOJLANISH YO'NALISHLARI	304
Abdusalomov Ozodbek Baxtiyor o'g'li XIZMAT KO'RSATISH KORXONALARINING IQTISODIY XAVFSIZLIGINI TA'MINLASHDA SERVIS XAVFSIZLIGI INDEKSI: SAMARQAND VILOYATI MISOLIDA	311
Shodmanova Zubayda Ubaydullayevna O'ZBEKISTONDA EKSPORTNI OSHIRISHDA AKT RIVOJLANISHINING O'RNI.....	315
Sadriddinov Ulug'bek Jaloliddin o'g'li QURILISH FAOLIYATI SOHALARIDA RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALARDAN FOYDALANISHNING ILG'OR XORIJIY TAJRIBALARI.....	322
Xusanov Kamoliddin Xolmamat o'g'li INSON KAPITALI VA KADRLAR SALOHİYATINI BOSHQARISHNING NAZARIY KONSEPSIYALARI	326
Abdullo Sohibov SUN'YI INTELLEKT TEXNOLOGIYALARI ASOSIDA TIJORAT BANKLARIDA RISK-MENEJMENT SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISH	331
Davronov Sanjar Ziyotovich SUN'YI INTELLEKT TEXNOLOGIYALARI ASOSIDA BOSHQARUV QARORLARINI QABUL QILISH MEKANIZMLARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	336
Ashrapova Noilaxon Niyazxonovna ISHLAB CHIQRISH KORXONALARINI BOSHQARISHDA RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALARDAN FOYDALANISHNING XORIJIY TAJRIBASI TAHLILI VA UNGA ILMIY YONDASHUVLAR.....	340
Ochilov Baxtiyor Muminjonovich THEORETICAL AND METHODOLOGICAL FOUNDATIONS OF IFRS AND FINANCIAL REPORTING.....	346
Tojiboyev Abdullajon Kamoliddin ugli SIRKULYAR IQTISODIYOTGA O'TISH: MUAMMOLAR VA ISTIQBOLLAR.....	351
Astanakulov Olim Tashtemirovich Muxammad Id Balbaa (Muhammad Eid Balbaa) Habibe Elif Kutlugun (Habibe Elif Kutlugun) GLOBAL IQLIM O'ZGARISHI FONIDA EKOLOGIK SIYOSAT VA BARQAROR RIVOJLANISH STRATEGIYALARI.....	357
Xamzayev Abdushukur Xudoyqulovich INTERNATIONAL MARKETING STRATEGIES FOR UZBEKISTAN'S TEXTILE INDUSTRY: CHALLENGES, OPPORTUNITIES, AND ECONOMETRIC EVIDENCE.....	362
Aziz Kurbanovich Abdullaev Sarvarbek Allayev Erkin ugli Shavkat Asrolovich Ruziev DIRECTIONS FOR TOURISM DEVELOPMENT IN UZBEKISTAN BASED ON DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES	369
Mirzaev Kulmamat Djanzakovich TEMIR YO'L TRANSPORTIDA SOLIQQA TORTISHNING O'ZIGA XOS XUSUSIYATLARI TAHLILI ("O'ZBEKISTON TEMIR YO'LLARI" AJ MISOLIDA).....	373
Barotov Baxtiyor Vaxobovich CHIQUINDILARNI QAYTA ISHLASHNING IQTISODIY SAMARADORLIGI VA BARQAROR RIVOJLANISHDAGI O'RNI	377
Muxitdinova Kamola Alisherovna TRANSPORT LOGISTIKASIDA TAVAKKALCHILIKLARNI SUG'URTALASH: O'ZBEKISTON VA AQSH TAJRIBASI ASOSIDA TAQQOSIY TAHLIL.....	381
Jabborov Islom Xusan o'g'li YASHIL IQTISODIYOT SHAROITIDA XIZMAT KO'RSATISH KORXONALARINING IQTISODIY SALOHİYATINI BARQAROR BOSHQARISH.....	385
Xayrullayev Shaxram Yunus o'g'li	

RAQAMLI TRANSFORMATSIYA SHAROITIDA SERVIS KORXONALARIDA XIZMATLAR SIFATI BOSHQARUVINING ZAMONAVIY MODELLARI	392
Xudoyorov Lochinbek Bahromovich BIZNES JARAYONLARI MONITORINGI SAMARADORLIGINI BAHOLASH MEZONLARI VA KO'RSATKICHLARI.....	398
Dadajonova Madina Ravshan qizi SIRKULAR IQTISODIYOT KONSEPSIYASINI AMALGA OSHIRISHNI BAHOLASH KO'RSATKICHLARINI (INDIKATORLARINI) SHAKLLANTIRISH.....	403
Sharifxo'jayeva Xonzodaxon A'lo qizi TURIZM QISHLOQLARINI SHAKLLANTIRISH MEZONLARI VA INDIKATORLARI TIZIMI	408
Xudaynazarova Dilorom NODAVLAT OLIY TA'LIM MUASSASALARIDA MOLIYAVIY BOSHQARUV VA BOSHQARUV HISOB TIZIMINING AMALIYOTI: MUAMMOLAR VA TAKOMILLASHTIRISH YO'LLARI	416
Xojiboyev Muxiddin Shodimuxamedovich DAVLAT XARIDLARI JARAYONIDA XAVFLARNI IDENTIFIKATSIYA QILISH, TASNIFLASH VA RISKKA ASOSLANGAN ICHKI AUDITNI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH	421
Meliboyev Askar Eshmuratovich DEVELOPING GARMENT MANUFACTURING STRATEGY IN THE CONTEXT OF DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION	426
Mahbuba Rahmonova Feruza Mansurovna Ollokulova QORAQALPOG'ISTON RESPUBLIKASI QISHLOQ XO'JALIGIDA INVESTITSIYA SIYOSATINING IQTISODIY AHAMIYATI.....	430
Bakhit Mambetnazarov Atabek Tureev SOLIQ TUSHUMLARI VA MAJBURIY AJRATMALARNING DAVLAT MOLIYASIDAGI O'RNI: 2020-2025 YILLAR TAHLILI VA ISTIQBOLI.....	434
Olimov Shukurulla Dilshodjon o'g'li ФАКТОРЫ ТЕКУЧЕСТИ КАДРОВ И МЕХАНИЗМЫ УДЕРЖАНИЯ ПЕРСОНАЛА В СОВРЕМЕННЫХ ОРГАНИЗАЦИЯХ УЗБЕКИСТАНА	439
Джураева Гузаль Шавкатовна XIZMAT KO'RSATISH SOHASIDA KICHIK KORXONALAR IQTISODIY SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISH MEKANIZMLARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	447
Mamirov Zamir Uzoq o'g'li XORIJIIY TO'G'RIDAN-TO'G'RI INVESTITSIYALARNI JALB ETISHDA O'ZBEKISTON TAJRIBASI: MUAMMOLAR VA ISTIQBOLLAR.....	453
Xatamov Nurbek Ochildiyevich DAVLAT BYUDJETI XARAJATLARI HISOB VA TAHLILINING AMALDAGI TIZIMI	458
Ostonokulov Azamat Abdulkarimovich Tursinbaev Gafur Jolmurzaevich MOLIYAVIY HISOBOTLAR AUDITINI XALQARO STANDARTLAR ASOSIDA TAKOMILLASHTIRISH ISTIQBOLLARI.....	464
Elomonov Dadaxon Ozodullayevich СТРАХОВАНИЕ КАК ИНСТРУМЕНТ СНИЖЕНИЯ ФИНАНСОВЫХ ПОТЕРЬ ОТ НЕПРЕДВИДЕННЫХ РИСКОВ, ОКАЗЫВАЮЩИХ ВЛИЯНИЕ НА ПРЕДПРИНИМАТЕЛЬСКУЮ ПРИБЫЛЬ (ДОХОД).....	470
Азимжон Мелиев Муродулло угли A STUDY ON THE COLLABORATIVE MECHANISM OF DIGITAL ARCHIVES GOVERNANCE AND TALENT GOVERNANCE: AN ANALYSIS BASED ON JOB COMPETENCY, PERFORMANCE EVALUATION, AND ORGANIZATIONAL EFFECTIVENESS	475
Wang Biao	

SANOAT KORXONALARI INNOVATSION SALOHİYATINI BAHOLASH METODIKASINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH	481
Bahodirov Shohruh Bahodir o'g'li	
QIMMATLI QOG'OZLAR BOZORINI TARTIBGA SOLISHNING XALQARO TAJRIBASI.....	488
Mallabayev Jobir Baxtiyorovich	
ANALYSIS OF THE FINANCIAL AND ECONOMIC ACTIVITY REPORTS OF OOO SAM TRADING STROY	493
Usmonova Dilfuza Ilhomovna	
WAYS TO IMPROVE THE USE OF FOREIGN EXPERIENCE IN THE TRANSPORT AND LOGISTICS CLUSTER IN THE NEW UZBEKISTAN.....	500
Musayeva Shoirazimovna	
FOUNDATIONS FOR THE SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT OF TRANSPORT LOGISTICS IN UZBEKISTAN	507
Muradov Alisher Kurbanbaevich	
DAVLAT MULKINI BOSHQARISHNING INNOVATSION VA RAQAMLI MEXANIZMLARINI RIVOJLANTIRISH ISTIQBOLLARI.....	513
Musurmonqulov Muhammad Ural o'g'li	
KORXONALARNING INVESTITSIYA FAOLIYATINI STRATEGIK BOSHQARISH: NAZARIYA VA ZAMONAVIY YONDASHUVLAR INTEGRATSIYASI.....	521
No'monjonova Muazzam Mahbubjon qizi	
KORXONALARDA DEBITORLIK VA KREDITORLIK QARZLARNI BOSHQARISHNING INNOVATSION YONDASHUVLARI VA ULARNI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH YO'NALISHLARI	526
Mirzaev Ozod Furkatovich	
INVESTITSIYA LOYIHALARINI MOLİYALASHTIRISH MEXANIZMLARINI RIVOJLANTIRISH: GIDROENERGETIKA SEKTORI MISOLIDA.....	531
Xusanov Shaxbozbek Shuxratjon o'g'li	
ТЕХНОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ ИННОВАЦИИ В КРАУДФАНДИНГЕ: БЛОКЧЕЙН, ИИ И БУДУЩЕЕ ИНВЕСТИРОВАНИЯ	538
Хамидова Фарิดахон Абдулкарим кизи	
Каримова Азиза Аъзамиддин кизи	
BANK TIZIMIDA QO'LLANILADIGAN RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALARNING TURLARI VA RIVOJLANISH BOSQICHLARI	545
Ollokulova Feruza Mansurovna	
Xursanova Shaxnoza Anvar qizi	
TA'LIM MUASSASALARIDA QO'SHIMCHA TA'LIM XIZMATLARINI BOSHQARISHNING NAZARIY YONDASHUVLARI	549
Safarova Kamola Shuxrat qizi	
QASHQADARYO VILOYAT MINTAQASINING IQTISODIY XAVFSIZLIK DARAJASI VA UNI BAHOLASH USLUBIYATI	553
Nurxonov Komiljon Tovkarayevich	
AYOLLARGA NISBATAN ZO'RAVONLIKNING IQTISODIY OQIBATLARI VA UNI KAMAYTIRISHNING BARQAROR RIVOJLANISHDAGI O'RNI.....	562
Feruza Bahodirxonovna Ibragimova	
ИНВЕСТИЦИОННЫЙ И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЙ ПОТЕНЦИАЛ ТУРИЗМА В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ: СТРУКТУРНЫЕ ТРАНСФОРМАЦИИ И НОВЫЕ ИСТОЧНИКИ РАЗВИТИЯ	567
Насиров Дилшод Фархадович	
Асадов Амалъжон Мехрожевич	
Ахматов Алинур Дилшодович	

ТЕОРЕТИЧЕСКИЕ МОДЕЛИ ИННОВАЦИОННОГО РАЗВИТИЯ ЭКОНОМИКИ	572
Насиров Дилшод Фархадович Хамраева Севара Мамуржановна Бахтиярова Алтынгул Бахтияровна	
INVESTITSION JOZIBADORLIKKA TA'SIR QILUVCHI OMILLAR TAHLILI	579
Mamatqulova Hafiza Bahodir qizi	
ЦИФРОВЫЕ ПЛАТФОРМЫ КАК НОВАЯ ФОРМА ОРГАНИЗАЦИИ БИЗНЕСА – ЭВОЛЮЦИЯ УПРАВЛЕНИЯ И ИНСТИТУЦИИ	586
Рахмонов Хумоюн Рустамжон угли	
XORIJIIY BANKLARNING YANGI BOZORLARGA KIRISH STRATEGIYALARI VA ULARNING MILLIY BANK TIZIMLARIGA TA'SIRI ("IПОТЕКА-BANK" AKSIYADORLIK TIJORAT BANKI MISOLIDA)	598
Kadirov Vaxid Marimbayevich Rajabboyeva Asalxon Mahmud qizi	
OECD VA YEVRONA ITTIFOQI MAMLAKATLARIDA BILVOSITA SOLIQA TORTISH TIZIMLARINING QIYOSIY TAHLILI VA O'ZBEKISTONDA UNI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH ISTIQBOLLARI	605
Tuxliyev Bozor Karimovich Dusiyarov Sherzod Xolmuratovich	
JISMONIY TARBIYANING INSON SALOMATLIGINI MUSTAHKAMLASHDAGI ROLI	614
Abdilaxatov Zafar Abdigapirovich	
СОВЕРШЕНСТВОВАНИЕ ОРГАНИЗАЦИОННО-ФУНКЦИОНАЛЬНОЙ СТРУКТУРЫ УПРАВЛЕНИЯ ПРОЕКТАМИ ИНТЕЛЛЕКТУАЛЬНОЙ ТАМОЖНИ	621
Ли Ирина Валентиновна	
JAHON IQTISODIYOTIDA O'ZBEKISTONNI TUTGAN O'RNI VA UNI RIVOJLANTIRISH YO'LLARI	627
Boboqulov Sanjar Bahromqulovich	
OBODONLASHTIRISH XIZMATLARI IJTIMOIIY MECHANIZMINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH	633
Hayitov Jamshid Xolvoyevich Ibragimova Gulhayo Nuriddin qizi	
O'ZBEKISTON SUG'URTA BOZORI TAHLILI	638
Hamroyeva Sabina Ismoil qizi	
EXPLORATION OF TOURISM FLOW GENERATING IN SAMARKAND UNDER THE BACKGROUND OF DIGITAL ECONOMY	644
Jie YANG	
ПЕРСПЕКТИВЫ РАЗВИТИЯ ОЗДОРОВИТЕЛЬНОГО ТУРИЗМА В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ	651
Усманова Диляфруз Каршиевна	
YASHIL ISTE'MOL XULQ-ATVORINI SHAKLLANTIRISH OMILLARI VA STRATEGIK ISTIQBOLLARI	656
Ishmuratov Baxodir Xusanovich	
O'ZBEKISTONDA INFLYATSIYA VA FOIZ SIYOSATINING BANK KREDITLARIGA TA'SIRI	661
Ibragimova Saule Orinbaevna	
IJTIMOIIY HIMOYA TIZIMI SAMARADORLIGINI BAHOLASHDA IJTIMOIIY-IQTISODIY KO'RSATKICHLARNING ROLI: STATISTIK YONDASHUV	665
Qurbonboyev Abdulla Mansur o'g'li	
O'ZBEKISTONDA INFLYATSIYAGA QARSHI KURASH DASTURINI AMALGA OSHIRISH YO'NALISHLARI	671
Murtazayev Ulug'bek Abdusalom o'g'li	
XARAJATLAR HISOBINI YURUTISHNING ZAMONAVIY USULLARI TAHLILI	675
Xasanov Baxodir Akramovich Yo'lchiyev Oybek Ulug'bek o'g'li	

SUG'URTA KOMPANIYALARINING MOLIVAVIY RISKLARINI KOMPLEKS BAHOLASH METODOLOGIYASI	683
Baymuratova Gulirayxon Tursunbayevna	
RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALAR ASOSIDA BARQAROR TURIZMNI RIVOJLANTIRISH.....	688
Ibragimov Husen Ismailovich	
KONSALTING XIZMATLARINING RIVOJLANISH EVOLYUTSIYASI VA RAQAMLI TRANSFORMATSIYASI	692
Ermamatova Shoxsanam Ermamat qizi	
GLOBAL BRANDING VS. LOCAL BRANDING: STRATEGIC TRADE-OFFS IN INTERNATIONAL MARKETING	698
Aziz Kurbanovich Abdullaev	
Mamasolieva Kamila	
Akhmedova Zaynabkhon Khayrullo qizi	

GLOBAL BRANDING VS. LOCAL BRANDING: STRATEGIC TRADE-OFFS IN INTERNATIONAL MARKETING

Aziz Kurbanovich Abdullaev

Acting Associate Professor

Department of International Finance and Investment

University of World Economy and Diplomacy

E-mail: aabdullayev@uwed.uz

ORCID: 0000-0002-4888-1068

Mamasolieva Kamila

University of World Economy and Diplomacy, Faculty of MEM

Major: Foreign Economic Activity

Phone: +998 97 422 09 55

E-mail: mamasolievakamila288@gmail.com

Akhmedova Zaynabkhon Khayrullo qizi

University of World Economy and Diplomacy, Faculty of MEM

Major: Foreign Economic Activity

Phone: +998 97 111 40 27

E-mail: axmedovazayka2003@gmail.com

Annotatsiya. Mazkur maqolada xalqaro marketingda global brending va lokal brending strategiyalarining o'zaro farqlari, afzalliklari hamda cheklovlari tahlil qilingan. Tadqiqotda Nike, Apple, Anta Sports va Xiaomi kompaniyalari misolida brend strategiyalarining bozor ulushi, daromad o'sishi, iste'molchi sodiqligi va raqobatbardoshlikka ta'siri o'rganilgan. Natijalar shuni ko'rsatadiki, global brendlar xalqaro tan olinishi, barqaror imiji va premium narxlash imkoniyati bilan ajralib turadi. Lokal brendlar esa madaniy moslashuvchanlik, mos narx siyosati va iste'molchilar bilan yaqin aloqalari orqali ustunlikka ega. Tadqiqot yakunida global identifikatsiya va mahalliy moslashuvni uyg'unlashtirgan gibrid strategiya eng samarali yondashuv sifatida baholangan.

Kalit so'zlar: global brending, lokal brending, xalqaro marketing, iste'molchi xulqi, bozor ulushi, gibrid strategiya, raqobatbardoshlik.

Аннотация. В данной статье исследуются стратегические различия между глобальным и локальным брендингом в международном маркетинге, а также их преимущества и ограничения. На примере компаний Nike, Apple, Anta Sports и Xiaomi проанализировано влияние бренд-стратегий на рыночную долю, рост доходов, лояльность потребителей и конкурентоспособность. Результаты показывают, что глобальные бренды обладают преимуществами благодаря высокой узнаваемости, стабильному имиджу и возможностям премиального позиционирования. Локальные бренды демонстрируют сильные позиции за счёт культурной адаптации, гибкой ценовой политики и тесной связи с потребителями. По итогам исследования сделан вывод, что наиболее эффективной является гибридная стратегия, сочетающая глобальную идентичность и локальную адаптацию.

Ключевые слова: глобальный брендинг, локальный брендинг, международный маркетинг, поведение потребителей, рыночная доля, гибридная стратегия, конкурентоспособность.

Abstarct. This article examines the strategic differences between global branding and local branding in international marketing, including their advantages and limitations. Using the cases of Nike, Apple, Anta Sports, and Xiaomi, the study analyzes the impact of branding strategies on market share, revenue growth, consumer loyalty, and competitiveness. The findings show that global brands benefit from international recognition, consistent image, and premium positioning opportunities. Local brands gain advantages through cultural adaptation, flexible pricing, and closer consumer relationships. The study concludes that a hybrid strategy combining global identity with local responsiveness is the most effective approach for sustainable success in international markets.

Keywords: global branding, local branding, international marketing, consumer behavior, market share, hybrid strategy, competitiveness.

INTRODUCTION

When companies choose to expand beyond their domestic markets, they are often faced with important strategic decisions regarding whether to present the same brand identity worldwide (global branding) or to modify the brand identity and marketing approach for each country in which they operate. This major question of whether to use a single global brand or develop multiple local brands represents one of the most significant aspects of international marketing and has a substantial influence on the overall success of a company's business activities.

A global brand is a brand, product, or service that has widespread recognition, presence, and reputation throughout the world, or at least in most key global regions, and whose value, image, and offerings remain relatively consistent across geographic boundaries.

At the same time, a global branding strategy does not eliminate opportunities for localization. For instance, The North Face, a global brand offered by the technologically advanced outdoor products manufacturer that is part of VF Corporation, has recently launched the "Asian Fit" line in China to better accommodate the sizing preferences of Asian consumers. This modification is clearly indicated on the product label.

Many businesses implement global branding strategies in which all aspects of branding—including products, logos, marketing messages, and complete brand identities—remain similar across markets worldwide. The objective is to ensure that consumers around the globe recognize the same brand and associate it with consistent value, regardless of where they live.

Examples of successful companies demonstrating a strong use of global branding include Nike. In its annual report, Nike reported total revenue of \$46.3 billion in 2024, supported by consistent branding campaigns such as "Just Do It," promoted through television, radio, and digital media with minimal variation across different markets. This consistency has enabled Nike to strengthen its social media presence, gain visibility at major sporting events worldwide, and establish retail operations in the majority of countries through its global store chain model.

Apple is another notable example. While many companies adopt significantly different advertising approaches across various parts of the world, Apple has maintained a strong and consistent core brand message centered on innovation, simplicity, and high-quality design, regardless of whether it is advertising in Tokyo, London, or New York City. In the four-quarter period ending 2024-09-28, Apple sold approximately 215 million iPhones worldwide and generated nearly \$383 billion in revenue across all markets combined. This consistency in brand strategy is one of the key factors that has made Apple one of the most recognized brands internationally.

Conversely, many companies do not adopt a single-message-fits-all approach. Numerous firms have achieved success through extensive localization of their brands across different cultures worldwide. A strong example is Anta Sports, a domestic Chinese sportswear company that has established a market position distinct from Nike or Adidas.

Anta combines culture and community in its local marketing campaigns. These often include promotions centered on national sporting events and feature prominent Chinese athletes who are admired as role models by the consumers the company aims to reach. By 2023, Anta's revenue reached ¥62.4 billion (approximately \$8.65 billion), growing at a faster rate than Nike in the Chinese market and representing approximately 23% of the Chinese sports apparel market.

Xiaomi began as a Chinese consumer electronics company and built its brand through close monitoring of local user feedback on online forums, adapting its product offerings based on customer requests. In 2024, Xiaomi's total revenue was reported at ¥365.9 billion, approximately 35% higher than in 2022. Xiaomi markets its products in non-Chinese markets by emphasizing product value in relation to local purchasing habits rather than applying a single international marketing strategy.

These contrasting approaches to branding encourage both researchers and practitioners to examine the importance of strategies used in developing global and local brands. Scholars have long debated whether multinational corporations should apply standardized or adapted marketing strategies worldwide. However, relatively few studies have directly compared global corporations with strong local brands, and in many industries there remains limited research comparing the performance of multinational corporations with successful domestic competitors.

The goal of this study is to address this knowledge gap by examining the effects of global and local branding strategies on consumer perceptions and market performance in international markets through selected brand case studies, with particular focus on the sportswear and consumer electronics industries.

The primary research question of the study is: In what ways do global versus local branding strategies influence consumer perception and market performance in international markets?

To answer this question, the study compares multinational brands with highly standardized branding (such as Nike and Apple) to locally rooted successful brands (such as Anta and Xiaomi), focusing on differences in marketing approaches, consumer engagement, and measurable business outcomes. This comparison is important not only for scholars but also for managers who must determine how to position their brands internationally.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Over the years, marketing scholars have actively engaged in the debate between global and local branding. In recent years, this discussion has become even more relevant due to developments in digital technology, global distribution channels, and the rapid growth of emerging markets. One of the most widely cited arguments in the literature is that global branding creates competitive advantages through consistency, efficiency, and economies of scale. David Aaker argues that the more consistent a brand remains over time, the greater its long-term value becomes. Strong brands benefit from consistency because consumers worldwide clearly understand what the brand represents and what it offers. This perspective lies at the core of many multinational corporations that prefer to maintain one unified global image rather than develop multiple local identities.

Some empirical studies support this view. Aysegul Özsoy and Selin Altaras conducted research on global branding across 14 countries over two waves spanning approximately 20 years. Their findings indicated a strong relationship between local consumer familiarity with a global company's name and the level of trust placed in that company, particularly when firms invested sufficiently in local advertising. The study also found that global brands were better known and more respected by consumers in 2021 than they had been in 2002. This suggests that global advertising has become more effective over time, largely because consumers now have broader access to international media through the internet and increased international travel opportunities.

It has also been suggested that consumers worldwide have become increasingly homogeneous, allowing firms to implement more efficient global marketing campaigns. Scholars such as Cătălin Dimofte and Irina Drăgan emphasize that understanding common global consumer trends can improve campaign efficiency.

However, a growing body of literature indicates that cultural factors continue to play a highly significant role in consumer behavior, and many marketing campaigns may lose effectiveness when they fail to account for local cultural contexts. Referring to research by Jan-Benedict E. M. Steenkamp, it has been argued that while many consumers understand the messages communicated by global brands, fewer consumers necessarily prefer to purchase them. In countries with strong cultural identities, such as China, India, and Brazil, local brands often perform more successfully when promoted through culturally relevant marketing strategies.

Research further suggests that the more closely a product aligns with the cultural values and preferences of a specific country, the greater its likelihood of success. This may require offering significantly different versions of the same product across markets, indicating that firms sometimes face a strategic trade-off between cultural alignment and global brand consistency. Consumers in culturally conscious markets often prefer products perceived as national or locally connected rather than those viewed as distant global alternatives. Therefore, in certain markets, promoting a strong local brand can be an especially effective marketing strategy.

Consumer behavior and marketing studies suggest that numerous additional factors—including price, the value consumers assign to a product, and the cultural meaning they attribute to it—play a significant role in determining how a brand is positioned in the global marketplace. For example, in the study *Exploring Cross-Cultural Consumer Behavior* by Zhang and Khare (2022), the authors found that consumers in emerging markets place substantially greater value on products that offer strong value for money and that reflect the cultural context of their countries. By contrast, consumers in developed markets tend to assign relatively lower importance to these same attributes. As a result, a global brand with a premium price position and a standardized product range may not achieve the same level of success in every market.

Another concept that has gained increasing attention in recent marketing research is the perceived localness of a brand. Swoboda, Pennemann, and Taube argue that even for major global corporations, localness can become an effective marketing instrument when supported by appropriate brand communication and localized sales activities. Their study suggests that a hybrid strategy—combining a globally standardized product and value proposition managed by headquarters with selective local adaptation implemented by regional subsidiaries—can often generate significantly higher consumer awareness, stronger brand associations, and greater preference than relying solely on pure global standardization or purely local branding.

Consumer goods companies increasingly expand their market presence through such hybrid strategies that combine both global and local elements. A notable example can be seen in multinational companies operating in China's fast-moving consumer goods sectors. Research has documented how companies such as Starbucks and Coca-Cola maintain a recognizable global image that reflects their core "brand DNA," while simultaneously adapting store design, seasonal product offerings, and marketing communication on platforms such as WeChat and Sina Weibo to local consumer preferences in China.

An important conclusion from this stream of research is that global and local branding should not necessarily be viewed as mutually exclusive alternatives, but rather as points along a strategic continuum from which companies may select the most suitable combination.

Although substantial knowledge exists regarding the drivers of both global brand success and local brand success, two major gaps remain in the current literature. First, much of the existing research focuses either on theoretical models that simplify real-world business dynamics or on specific country-to-country comparisons. Consequently, relatively limited

research examines the practical impact of branding strategies that firms actually implement across entire product categories and industries.

Second, there is still limited comparative analysis of the different marketing strategies employed by large diversified global corporations and strong domestic firms in developing markets. Existing studies often focus either on global firms operating independently in home and host markets or on the success of local firms only within their domestic environment, with relatively little comparison between firms that possess comparable scale, reach, and resources across different contexts.

This study seeks to address both gaps by investigating a representative sample of globally recognized brands—such as Nike and Apple—and strong local competitors such as Anta Sports and Xiaomi. Comparative analysis of these global and local brands enables the examination of how different branding strategies are applied and how they relate to key performance indicators, consumer attitudes, and competitive positioning.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study adopts a comparative case study design to analyze differences between global and local branding strategies. Companies from the sportswear and consumer electronics industries were selected because these sectors are highly brand-dependent and include both dominant global players and strong local competitors. Therefore, these industries provide an appropriate context for comparing alternative branding strategies and market orientations.

Case Selection

Four companies were selected because they represent two contrasting branding approaches:

Nike – a highly globalized brand in the sportswear industry.

Apple – a globally standardized brand in consumer electronics.

Anta Sports – a strong domestic Chinese sportswear brand expanding internationally.

Xiaomi – a Chinese electronics brand characterized by local adaptation and growing global market share.

These companies were chosen because of the contrasting nature of their branding strategies. Some global corporations maintain highly standardized brand portfolios, whereas local competitors adopt adaptive branding approaches suited to domestic market environments. Several of these firms have achieved notable success through either strong standardization or effective localization.

Data Sources

The study is based on secondary data collected from multiple reliable sources, including:

Company annual reports (Nike 2024, Apple 2024, Anta 2023, Xiaomi 2024);

Market research databases such as Statista and Euromonitor International;

Academic articles published during 2021–2025 related to branding, international marketing, and consumer behavior;

Credible business media and industry analysis, including China Daily and sector-specific analytical platforms.

Using multiple data sources allows cross-verification of evidence, reduces bias associated with reliance on a single source, and strengthens the validity of the study's conclusions.

Variables and Measures

To compare brands across industries, several analytical variables were constructed.

Independent Variables (Brand Strategy Factors)

Brand globalization – degree of consistency in brand identity, messaging, and positioning across markets;

Cultural flexibility – extent of adaptation in communication, product features, or services to local cultural needs;

Pricing policy – premium, value-based, or mixed pricing orientation;

Communication method – balance between global and local promotional activities;

Market positioning strategy – leadership, premium, or mass-market orientation.

Dependent Variables (Performance and Perception Indicators)

Market penetration rate – share of customers using the brand within a region;

Consumer perception – familiarity, trust, and positive attitudes toward the brand;

Brand loyalty – retention and repurchase intentions;

Competitive standing – relative market position compared with competitors.

Analytical Approach

A mixed-method approach combining quantitative and qualitative analysis was employed.

Quantitative Analysis

Comparisons of market share, revenue, and sales volume were conducted using company reports and industry databases.

Qualitative Analysis

Marketing campaigns, pricing strategies, customer engagement methods, and adaptation to local needs were examined through company press releases, advertisements, and public communications.

Justification of the Methodology

The comparative case study method was considered appropriate because it:

Enables strong cross-company comparisons in highly brand-dependent industries;

Demonstrates the effects of strategic branding differences;

Provides practical insights for managerial decision-making;

Allows detailed contextual analysis using accessible secondary data;

Offers a framework for evaluating trade-offs between cost efficiency, global visibility, and customer acceptance.

By integrating quantitative and qualitative findings, the study evaluates how strategic branding choices influence both consumer perceptions and business performance.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

This section presents a comparison of global and local branding strategies using revenue, market share, and marketing practices for the selected companies: Nike, Apple, Anta, and Xiaomi. The analysis is based on financial reports, industry databases, and verified media sources (Table 1).

Table 1
Comparison of the Revenue of Global and Local Brands

Brand	2023 Revenue (USD)	2024 Revenue (USD)	Year-on-Year Growth	Source
Nike	44.5 B	46.3 B	+4%	Nike Annual Report 2024
Apple	378 B	383 B	+1.3%	Apple Annual Report 2024
Anta Sports	7.45 B	8.65 B	+16%	China Daily / Kr-Asia
Xiaomi	271 B CNY (~39.5 B USD)	365.9 B CNY (~53.3 B USD)	+35%	EcommerceUpdate.org

Source: Nike (2024); Apple (2024); Anta (2023); Xiaomi (2024).

Nike and Apple maintain substantial global revenues; however, their growth rates are relatively moderate compared to strong local brands operating in emerging markets.

Anta Sports and Xiaomi demonstrate strong growth in domestic markets, reflecting the effectiveness of local adaptation strategies and culturally relevant marketing approaches (Table 2).

Table 2
Market Share Analysis (China Example)

Brand	Market Share (Sportswear)	Market Share (Electronics)	Source
Nike	20.7%	–	Euromonitor
Anta Sports	23.0%	–	Euromonitor
Apple	–	20.0%	IDC 2025
Xiaomi	–	13.1%	IDC 2025

Source: Euromonitor (2024); IDC (2025).

As can be seen from the table, local brands such as Anta Sports and Xiaomi outperform global competitors in certain market segments due to stronger cultural alignment, more flexible pricing strategies, and locally tailored marketing activities. Global brands continue to maintain strong recognition and prestige; however, they may experience slower adoption in price-sensitive or culturally distinctive markets.

3. Marketing Approach Observations

An analysis of how these companies manage marketing reveals clear differences between global and local brands. These differences extend beyond advertising campaigns and include the broader ways in which brands are built, positioned, and connected with consumers. Global brands generally rely on standardized strategies designed to function consistently across many markets.

For example, Nike applies its well-known “Just Do It” concept globally with only limited adaptation, such as changes in language or the athletes featured in advertisements. The central message—self-improvement, ambition, and achieve-

ment—remains largely universal. This consistency strengthens brand recognition and may also reduce marketing costs by avoiding the need to redesign campaigns for each country.

Apple follows a similar model. Its product launches and promotional campaigns consistently emphasize minimalist design, innovation, and user-friendly technology. Even in markets with distinct cultural preferences, Apple generally preserves the same premium global identity. This strategy reinforces exclusivity and supports premium pricing across international markets.

By contrast, local brands such as Anta Sports place greater emphasis on themes that are directly relevant to domestic consumers. Anta incorporates elements of Chinese culture into its campaigns, including partnerships with national athletes and sponsorship of locally significant sporting events. Rather than promoting a broad global narrative, the company builds a more personal and culturally connected relationship with consumers. This can strengthen emotional attachment and brand loyalty.

Xiaomi represents another adaptive model. The company places strong emphasis on digital interaction, communicating directly with consumers through online communities and feedback platforms. Instead of relying solely on one-way promotional messaging, Xiaomi uses customer input to refine products, services, and communication strategies. This creates a dynamic branding model that responds quickly to changing consumer needs.

Overall, the global branding approach prioritizes consistency, scale, and long-term recognition, while local branding emphasizes flexibility, relevance, and close consumer connection. In practice, successful international marketing often requires balancing these two approaches depending on the specific characteristics of each market.

4. Consumer Perception and Loyalty

Consumer perception of brands is closely linked to the marketing differences discussed earlier and has a significant influence on long-term customer loyalty. Loyalty is determined not only by product quality, but also by the extent to which a brand aligns with cultural expectations, responds to price sensitivity, and creates emotional connections with consumers.

Global brands such as Nike and Apple benefit from strong international recognition. Consumers often associate these brands with reliability, innovation, prestige, and aspirational lifestyles. In developed markets particularly, purchasing such brands may symbolize social status or lifestyle preferences. As a result, many consumers remain loyal despite premium pricing.

However, this pattern does not apply equally across all markets. In emerging economies, where purchasing power may be more limited, consumers often place greater emphasis on value for money. In these contexts, global brands may be perceived as expensive or less aligned with everyday consumer needs. Although brand awareness remains high, repeat purchases and long-term loyalty may be lower among price-sensitive segments.

Local brands frequently perform better in emotional and cultural dimensions because they align more closely with domestic traditions, values, and consumer expectations. For example, Anta Sports positions itself through themes of national pride and support for local athletes, creating trust and a stronger sense of belonging among consumers. Such cultural familiarity can be difficult for global competitors to replicate. This connection often strengthens loyalty, particularly in markets where cultural identity strongly influences purchasing behavior.

Xiaomi combines affordability with active consumer engagement to build repeat purchasing behavior. The company offers competitive technical specifications at relatively accessible prices, attracting budget-conscious consumers. At the same time, Xiaomi maintains direct communication with users, allowing them to feel involved in product development and brand evolution. This participatory relationship can increase emotional attachment and customer retention.

Responsiveness is another important factor. Local brands are often able to react more quickly to changing consumer preferences by launching new products, adjusting features, or modifying marketing strategies. This flexibility helps them remain relevant in rapidly changing markets and further strengthens customer loyalty.

Overall, global brands are highly effective in creating aspirational value and prestige, while local brands often outperform in cultural relevance, value perception, and adaptability. Therefore, customer loyalty depends less on brand size alone and more on how effectively the brand responds to the specific needs of each market.

5. Key Findings

1. Revenue growth is higher for local brands in emerging markets despite smaller absolute revenues.
2. Market share data indicate that cultural adaptation and pricing strategies directly influence competitive positioning.
3. Consumer engagement is stronger for brands that combine product relevance with cultural identity.
4. Global consistency and local adaptation should not be viewed as mutually exclusive; hybrid strategies (global identity with local adaptation) often provide balanced advantages.

Brand Stretching in China: Balancing Global and Local Branding

The aim of this study is to examine the global–local branding dilemma within the context of the emerging China market by comparing four internationally recognized brands that have operated in China’s sportswear and technology sectors for several years: Nike, Apple, Anta Sports, and Xiaomi.

Advantages of Global Branding

1. Strong International Recognition

Global brands often remain highly memorable across markets. Companies such as Nike and Apple maintain a consistent identity worldwide, making them easily recognizable in different countries. This consistency helps build long-term trust and strengthens overall brand equity.

2. Economies of Scale and Cost Efficiency

Global brands can also achieve cost advantages. By using similar advertising campaigns, product concepts, and communication strategies across markets, they reduce the need to redesign operations for each country. This lowers marketing and production costs while improving efficiency.

3. Premium Positioning

Another major advantage is premium market positioning. Global brands are frequently associated with innovation, prestige, and aspirational lifestyles, allowing them to charge higher prices. Consumers often perceive such brands as symbols of quality and status.

Advantages of Local Branding

1. Stronger Cultural Connection

Local brands often connect more effectively with domestic consumers because they reflect local traditions, values, and preferences. For example, Anta Sports is closely associated with Chinese identity and local consumer expectations, helping the company build trust and emotional closeness in its home market.

2. Flexible Pricing

Local brands can adapt pricing more easily to match local purchasing power. Unlike some global firms that maintain premium pricing strategies, domestic brands are often better positioned to compete in price-sensitive markets.

3. Greater Responsiveness

Local companies can often respond more quickly to changing consumer trends, economic conditions, and customer feedback. Xiaomi, for example, has built success through rapid product adjustments, user feedback integration, and flexible marketing responses. This agility is a major competitive advantage.

3. The Case for Hybrid Strategies

The findings of this study support the hybrid strategy perspective, which suggests that the most effective approach is often a balance between worldwide consistency and local flexibility. Global brands can preserve their core identity while adapting selected elements—such as advertising, product features, or distribution channels—to local market conditions.

For instance, Apple maintains the same core brand identity worldwide but adapts to local consumption habits and seasonal demand patterns. Similarly, Nike sometimes uses market-specific campaigns to reflect local events, sports culture, or social trends.

Therefore, successful brands often combine the advantages of global reputation with local customization. This enables firms to preserve worldwide prestige while simultaneously responding to the needs of consumers in diverse market environments.

4. Implications for Marketing Managers

No single branding strategy is universally effective under all circumstances. The success of any particular approach depends on multiple factors, including market structure, cultural characteristics, economic conditions, and the intensity of competition. As a result, different strategies may prove more effective in different environments. Local branding strategies may perform particularly well in developing markets, while global branding can often be more successful in developed markets where brand prestige and consistency are highly valued.

Managerial decisions should not be limited to short-term outcomes. Global branding can create substantial international brand equity, strengthen recognition, and provide a basis for premium pricing. However, local adaptation may be necessary to build stronger customer loyalty, improve market responsiveness, and support rapid expansion in markets characterized by strong cultural diversity or intense price competition.

Therefore, marketing managers should evaluate branding strategy as a dynamic decision rather than a fixed choice. In many cases, combining global identity with selective local adaptation may provide the most sustainable competitive advantage.

5. Limitations and Future Research

One limitation of this study is its reliance on secondary data, which may not fully capture all dimensions of consumer perceptions or the internal strategic decision-making processes of firms. Secondary sources are valuable for comparative analysis, but they may not always reflect real-time consumer attitudes or managerial intentions.

Future research could therefore benefit from the collection of primary data through surveys, interviews, or focus groups involving consumers and marketing managers. Such research may be conducted not only in the sportswear and technology sectors, but also in industries such as food services, retail, hospitality, and financial services.

Additional comparative studies across different countries and industries could provide deeper insight into the relative influence of global versus local brand names. This would help scholars and practitioners better understand how branding strategies should be adapted to changing international market conditions.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The analysis demonstrates that both global and local branding strategies offer distinct advantages, while companies that successfully combine elements of both approaches often achieve stronger overall performance. To secure long-term success in emerging markets, firms need to maintain an effective balance between global consistency, local cultural relevance, and sensitivity to market conditions.

The comparative case studies of Nike, Apple, Anta Sports, and Xiaomi indicate that global brands such as Nike and Apple benefit from stronger worldwide recognition, established prestige, and operational efficiency. However, local Chinese brands have demonstrated superior performance in several areas, including consumer engagement, market share growth, and customer loyalty, by implementing pricing and marketing strategies that align closely with domestic consumer preferences.

Overall, the findings suggest that neither pure global standardization nor complete localization is universally optimal. Instead, a balanced hybrid strategy that combines international brand strength with local market responsiveness appears to be the most effective path for sustainable competitive success.

REFERENCES

1. Nike (2024) *Form 10-K Annual Report 2024*. Available at: NIKE, Inc. Investor Relations – News, Events and Reports.
2. Apple (2024) *Form 10-K Annual Report 2024*. Available at: archive.org.
3. Anta Sports (2023) *Annual Report 2023*. Available at: ir.anta.com/en/financial_report_share.php
4. Xiaomi (2024) *Annual Report 2024*. Available at: ir.mi.com/financial-information/annual-interim-reports
5. Theodore Levitt (1983) 'The Globalization of Markets', *Harvard Business Review*.
6. Susan P. Douglas and C. Samuel Craig (2011) 'Convergence and Divergence: Developing a Global Marketing Strategy', *Journal of International Marketing*, 19(1), pp. 82–101.
7. Isabelle Schuiling and Jean-Noël Kapferer (2004) 'Real Differences Between Local and International Brands', *Journal of International Marketing*, 12(4), pp. 97–112.
8. Jan-Benedict E. M. Steenkamp, Rajeev Batra and Dana L. Alden (2003) 'How Perceived Brand Globalness Creates Brand Value', *Journal of International Business Studies*, 34(1), pp. 53–65.
9. Aysegul Özsoy (2012) 'The Interplay Between Global and Local Brands', *Journal of International Marketing*, 20(2), pp. 72–95.
10. Ilan Alon, Eugene Jaffe, Carsten Prange and Donata Vianelli (2017) *Global Marketing: Contemporary Theory, Practice, and Cases*. 2nd edn. Routledge.
11. Aziz Kurbanovich Abdullaev (2025) *International Marketing: A Manual*. University of World Economy and Diplomacy, Tashkent. 136 p.
12. International Data Corporation (2025) *Worldwide Smartphone Market Share*.
13. Deloitte (2023) *Global Marketing Trends*.
14. Deloitte (2023) *Global Marketing Trends*.

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Ingliz tili muharriri: Feruz Hakimov

Musahhih: Zokir ALIBEKOV

Sahifalovchi va dizayner: Oloviddin Sobir o'g'li

2026. № 4 (2)

© Materiallar ko'chirib bosilganda "Yashil" iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot" jurnali manba sifatida ko'rsatilishi shart. Jurnalda bosilgan material va reklamalardagi dalillarning aniqligiga mualliflar ma'sul. Tahririyat fikri har vaqt ham mualliflar fikriga mos kelmasligi mumkin. Tahririyatga yuborilgan materiallar qaytarilmaydi.

Mazkur jurnalda maqolalar chop etish uchun quyidagi havolalarga maqola, reklama, hikoya va boshqa ijodiy materiallar yuborishingiz mumkin. Materiallar va reklamalar pullik asosda chop etiladi.

EI.Pochta: sq143235@gmail.com

Bot: @iqtisodiyot_77

Tel.: 93 718 40 07

Jurnalga istalgan payt quyidagi rekvizitlar orqali obuna bo'lishingiz mumkin. Obuna bo'lgach, @iqtisodiyot_77 telegram sahifamizga to'lov haqidagi ma'lumotni skrinshot yoki foto shaklida jo'natishingizni so'raymiz. Shu asosda har oygi jurnal yangi sonini manzilingizga jo'natamiz.

"Yashil" iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot" jurnali 03.11.2022-yildan O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Adminstratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar agentligi tomonidan №566955 reyestr raqami tartibi bo'yicha ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

Litsenziya raqami: №046523. PNFL: 30407832680027

Manzilimiz: Toshkent shahar, Mirzo Ulug'bek tumani
Kumushkon ko'chasi, 26-uy.

Jurnal sayti: <https://yashil-iqtisodiyot-taraqqiyot.uz>